

Named Entity Recognition for Malayalam

Silja C K

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally,Kerala
siljack2022b@mca.ajce.in

Dr.T K Bijimol

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirapally,Kerala
tkbijimol@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—The process of identifying entities in a written document and categorizing them into predetermined categories such as Person, Location, Organization, and so on is known as named entity recognition. It is a vital phase in the natural language text processing process. The named entity recognition system is designed to extract useful data from the text. In Malayalam, various approaches are used for NER. In this research, we propose a Naive Bayes classifier-based NER system for Malayalam. NER structures characteristic properly in high-aid languages like English, however for low-aid languages like Malayalam, that is an Indian language spoken within side the nation of Kerala, there are few nicely-advanced NER structures.

Keywords—Named Entity Recognition, Information Extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

We now live in an era of information explosion, in which vast volumes of data in various formats, including text, audio, photos, video, and so on, are constantly being added to the Internet. Because of its unstructured nature, analyzing and uncovering valuable patterns from such massive data is always a difficult undertaking. Unstructured text, which has no specific format for representation, makes up a substantial portion of this data. Information extraction (IE) is a type of artificial intelligence (AI) that focuses on locating hidden facts in unstructured text data. Entities, key words, topics, relations, and other patterns of interest mentioned in the unstructured text corpus are extracted by IE.

This paper proposes an ML-based approach for NER for the Malayalam language. We use different DL algorithms such as Naïve Bayes, K nearest neighbor, Decision tree classifier to compare the NER performance. The major contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- Discusses NER for languages with limited resources, such as Malayalam.
- processing the dataset with Malayalam news headings, predict category in which Malayalam news headings belong.
- Compares accuracy of the NER.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The goal of NER for Malayalam research was to create and compare NER systems for the Malayalam language. This segment discusses several of the most famous and contemporary NER techniques. This studies on named entity recognition is split into sub sections: One covers modern strategies for English and different languages posted with inside the NLP literature, at the same time as the alternative covers NER methods pronounced with inside the literature for Malayalam NER. There are several NER methods in English, Chinese and other different resource-extensive languages. Some of the most famous works in those fields are indexed below.

One of the earlier approaches to recognizing named entities was the use of the HMM. The authors have used Hidden Markov Models (HMM) to perform natural language processing (NLP) for names, times, and numerical quantities. A recent study in Malayalam language NER was reported by Sreeja Pillai [1], in which the authors analyzed the challenges in NER and proposed a NER system for Malayalam using LSTM. Shruthi in 2016 published another work in NER. On NER, they compared TnT and MEMM's performance. There were very few sentences used for training Nita Patiletal is a mathematician who specializes in algebra and calculus. In 2016, [2] conducted a survey of NER systems with respect to Indian languages and foreign languages. In this survey, the authors discussed different approaches, strategies, and features that can be used to develop NER for different languages.

Lakshmi etal.[3] reported NER in Malayalam using fuzzy SVM. Contextual semantic rules and linguistic grammar rules were used to create this system. Although the method was able to resolve ambiguity created by typical SVM classifiers, the corpus size employed was limited. JishaP.Jayanetal.in2013[4] developed a NER for Malayalam in Hybrid Approach. For series labelling jobs, they employed TnT, an open-source statistical tagger. However, the educational corpus became so limited that they evolved into a NER in a closed domain. The first work in Malayalam was reported by Bind huetal.in2011 [5]. For NER, they combined linguistic concepts with statistical approaches. A

significant disadvantage was the small size of the training corpus.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this prediction system, we use Visual studio code that makes it easy to set up and access.

A. Requirements

- VS code
- CSV file
- Algorithm

B.NaiveBayes: The Naive Bayes algorithm is a probabilistic classification algorithm that is simple to use. It is based on a probabilistic model that includes strong independence assumptions. The assumption of independence is not always correct, as it may not have an impact on reality. Therefore, they are considered unsophisticated.

C.KNN Algorithm: The acronym KNN stands for "K-Nearest Neighbor." It is a supervised machine learning algorithm that has been carefully designed to produce accurate predictions. The algorithm can be used to solve both classification and regression problems. The number of variables that are most like a new unknown variable can be predicted or classified using the symbol 'K'.

D.Decision Tree: It is a classifier that is organized as a tree, with internal nodes representing the features of a dataset, branches representing the decision rules, and leaves representing the outcomes. A Decision tree has two nodes: a Decision Node and a Leaf Node. The Decision Node is the first node in the tree and the Leaf Node is the last node in the tree.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

Firstly, open your editor and create a new file, then import modules

```
import numpy as np
import nltk
from nltk.tokenize import sent_tokenize, word_tokenize
from nltk.stem import PorterStemmer
from nltk.stem import WordNetLemmatizer
from nltk.corpus import stopwords
from sklearn.datasets import load_files
import pandas as pd
import re
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.svm import SVC
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from gensim.models import Word2Vec
from gensim.models.doc2vec import Doc2Vec, TaggedDocument
from gensim.models import KeyedVectors
```

Figure 1: importing the module.

```
data.head()
```

	headings	label
0	കൊച്ചി ചെറുപ്പ് വിതരണ കേന്ദ്രത്തിലെ തീപിടിത്തം...	business
1	ഈശ്വരൻ കറി പഴയറിന് പു...	business
2	ശ്രീരാമൻ്റെ തൃജീവനാത്ത വിലക്ക് വിൽവലിച്ചു	sports
3	റയൽ മാഡ്രിഡിനെ തെട്ടിച്ച യുവതാരം ബ്രസീൽ ടീ...	sports
4	എനിക്ക് ശ്രീനിവാസൻ തൃക്കേട്ട, ലോഹിതദാസ് മതി: ക...	entertainment

Figure 2: Read dataset for the model training

```
score = model.evaluate(X_test, Y_test, verbose = 1, batch_size = 32)
print("Accuracy: %.2f" % (score[1]*100))
```

```
40/40 [=====] - 0s 11ms/step - loss: 0.6818 - accuracy: 0.8507
Accuracy: 85.07
```

Figure 3: Accuracy of naïve bayes algorithm

```
knn = KNeighborsClassifier(n_neighbors=2)
knn.fit(X_train, Y_train)
print(knn.predict(X_test))
p = knn.predict(X_test)
q = accuracy_score(Y_test, p)
print("accuracy of the algorithm is:", q)
```

```
[[0. 0. 0.]
 [0. 0. 0.]
 [0. 0. 1.]
 ...
 [0. 0. 0.]
 [0. 1. 0.]
 [0. 0. 0.]]
accuracy of the algorithm is: 0.276409849086576:
```

Figure 4: Accuracy of KNN algorithm

```
clf = DecisionTreeClassifier()

clf = clf.fit(X_train,Y_train)

y_pred = clf.predict(X_test)
print("Accuracy:",metrics.accuracy_score(Y_test, y_pred))
```

```
Accuracy: 0.6258935663224782
```

Figure 5: Accuracy of Decision tree algorithm

V. RESULT

This phase details the outcomes of the experiment, we have determined the accuracy of the experiment using Naive Bayes, KNN and Decision Tree classification algorithms. The accuracy obtained by using Naive bayes is 0.84, Accuracy obtained when using Decision tree is 0.62 and Accuracy obtained when using KNN algorithm is 0.24. When processing the dataset with Malayalam news headings, we got the result of the category in which Malayalam news headings belong.

```
test = pd.read_csv('DATA/malayalam_news_test.csv')
p=test
test.head()
```

	ID	headings
0	MAL_0001	അന്താരാഷ്ട്ര ഉന്റർനെറ്റ് സേവനം താരക്കോലികമ...
1	MAL_0002	മഞ്ഞ് ചതിച്ചുശരണം!!!, ഹാനോവറിന്റെ പ്രതീക്ഷക...
2	MAL_0003	12 സീസൺ എട്ടു ചാർബ്യൂമാർ, പ്രവചിക്കാൻ ...
3	MAL_0004	പുറംതൊഴിലുറയായു തൊറ്റിട്ടും യോഗ്യത നേടി ഗോവ...
4	MAL_0005	മദ്യപിച്ചെത്തിയ നടമാർ തമ്മിൽ കയ്യങ്കളി...

Figure 6: Read dataset for the testing

```
pred_labels=le.inverse_transform(class_label)
print(pred_labels)
```

['business' 'business' 'sports' ... 'sports' 'business' 'entertainment']

Figure 7: Prediction using Naive Bayes

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a machine learning algorithm for NER in Malayalam. This method uses different machine learning algorithms to compare the performance. The experiments carried out with the Malayalam information dataset display that the system getting to know processes have huge capability and supply higher accuracy. In this study, we can conclude that naive bayes have high accuracy compared with KNN and the Decision tree. Many language-computing algorithms evolved for low-aid languages, inclusive of in Indian language communities, might also additionally deliver higher accuracy if Machine Learning methods may be implemented.

VII. FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

I would like to expand this experiment to a much larger data set because the end findings of this planned effort are encouraging. It is also worth looking at tagging more data and publishing it for other language computing researchers with less resources. In the future, we can use these trained models to create a web application that will give a named entity tagger for Malayalam.

VIII. REFERENCES

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